

Synthesis, characterization and assessment of *in vitro* antimicrobial activities of tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes of azo-imino-*para*-carboxylates

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Abstract : Tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes of some azo-imino-*para*-carboxylates have been synthesized by reacting *para*-azo-benzoic acid ligand, i.e. 4-(3-formyl-4-hydroxy-phenylazo)-benzoic acid with triphenyltin(IV) hydroxide in anhydrous toluene and then condensed with appropriate aniline derivatives in absolute ethanol. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, UV, IR, ¹H, ¹³C and ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectroscopy. ¹¹⁹Sn NMR values for all the complexes fall within the range specified for 4-coordinate geometry indicating that the complexes have four-coordinate tetrahedral structures around tin atom in solution. The complexes were screened for their *in vitro* antimicrobial activities against various microbes and compared with standard drugs. All the tested tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes were found to exhibit effective antimicrobial activity.

Keywords : Tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes, *para*-azo-carboxylate, ¹¹⁹Sn NMR, antimicrobial activities.

Introduction

Organotin(IV) compounds exhibit a wide range of applications as fungicides and bactericides¹⁻³. Organotin(IV) compounds are important class of organometallic compounds because of their commercial use in industry as PVC stabilizing agents and also find applications in agriculture; as wood preservatives, fungicides and pesticides^{4,5}. Further, organotin(IV) compounds have also been used for their pharmacological applications such as anti-tumor^{6,7} and anti-tuberculosis agents⁸. Large number of organotin(IV) compounds were screened for their *in vitro* activity⁹⁻¹¹ against a variety of tumor cells and found to be more active than *cis*-platin⁹. Organotin(IV) compounds have also been studied owing to their possibility to exhibit large number of interesting diverse structures¹⁰⁻¹³. In general, the biochemical activity of organotin(IV) carboxylates are influenced to a great extent by their structures and the coordination number around tin atom in the complexes¹⁴. In addition to this, organotin(IV) carboxylates of a series of *ortho*-azo-carboxylate ligand systems have been studied in recent years because of their interesting structures¹⁵⁻¹⁷ and potential biological properties^{15,16}. Furthermore, synthesis, crystal structures and

toxicity studies on the *Aedes aegypti* and *Anopheles stephensi* mosquito larvae of tri-organotin(IV) complexes of some *para*-azo-carboxylate ligands viz. 4-(4-hydroxy-3-phenyliminomethyl-phenylazo)-benzoic acids were also reported¹⁸. The geometry of tri-organotin(IV) compounds were found to be monomeric tetrahedral structures and exhibited effective toxic properties against the mosquito larvae. Recently, we have also reported antimicrobial properties of tri-*n*-butyltin(IV) complexes of *para*-azo-carboxylates derived from substituted anilines and 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine and were found to be effective antimicrobial agents against the various screened microbes¹⁹. Thus, as part of our continuous effort to search better antimicrobial organotin(IV) compounds, in this paper we report the synthesis of some tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes of *para*-azo-carboxylate ligands viz. 4-(3-formyl-4-hydroxy-phenylazo)-benzoic acid and 4-(4-hydroxy-3-phenyliminomethyl-phenylazo)-benzoic acids. The complexes were obtained by the condensation of substituted aniline derivatives with tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes of 4-[(*E*)-2-(3-formyl-4-hydroxy-phenyl)-1-diazenyl]-benzoic acid following the analogous procedure reported earlier¹⁸. The ligand skeleton of the *para*-azo-carboxylate ligand

systems used in the synthesis of tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes are shown in Fig. 1[(a) and (b)] while the structural motifs shown by some tri-organotin(IV) complexes of *p*-azo-carboxylates reported earlier are shown in Scheme 1. The *in vitro* antimicrobial activities of the tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes were also investigated against various microbes and compared with some standard drugs.

Fig. 1. Generic structure of the ligands. Abbreviations : (a) LHH' (azo-preligand), (b) L¹HH', X : 4-NO₂; L²HH', 4-Cl; L³HH', 2-OH; L⁴HH', 4-SO₂NH₂; L⁵HH', 3-CH₃; L⁶HH', 2-CH₃ (condensed ligands with substituted anilines); where H and H' represent hydroxyl and carboxylic acid H atoms respectively.

(Ignoring weak and long bond between tin and chelating oxygen atom of carboxylate group, the geometry of tri-organotin(IV) complexes is considered to be tetrahedral)

Scheme 1. Structural motif shown by tri-organotin(IV) complexes of *para*-azo-carboxylates.

Results and discussion

Synthesis aspects :

The tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes of 4-(4-hydroxy-3-phenyliminomethyl-phenylazo)-benzoic acids (L¹⁻⁶HH') have been synthesized by the reaction of Ph₃SnLH with the substituted anilines in ethanol. Synthesis of the tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes, **1-6** [Ph₃SnL¹⁻⁶H] from the condensed ligands was not possible due to insolubility nature of the starting *p*-azo-benzoic acid ligand (LHH') in common organic solvents. Therefore, tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes of azo-carboxylate ligand was first synthesized by the reaction of LHH' with Ph₃SnOH in anhydrous toluene, and then condensed with appropriate substituted anilines in ethanol to give the desired compounds of the condensed azo-imino-carboxylate ligands in good yields and high purity (Reaction Scheme 1). The characterizations data of the tri-phenyltin(IV) compounds are given in experimental section. These compounds are stable in air and soluble in all common organic solvents.

Spectroscopic characterization :

UV-Visible spectra :

The UV-Visible spectra of compounds **1-6** were recorded in DMF solution (10⁻⁴ M) at room temperature. The electronic spectrum of LHH' showed absorptions at 247 and 322 nm assigned to π - π^* transition of aromatic ring and n - π^* transition of imine (C=N) group respectively²⁰. UV-Visible spectra of compounds **1-6** exhibited three absorption bands at 252–258, 356–378 and 455–477 nm, respectively. After coordination, π - π^* transition of aromatic ring and n - π^* transition of imine group were observed at slight higher wavelength in the complexes²¹. The new band observed at 455–477 nm indicated ligand to metal charge transfer. The slight increase of the λ_{\max} value from the ligand to the organotin(IV) complexes indicated coordination of ligand to tin atom.

IR spectra :

In IR spectra of the ligand, the antisymmetric [$\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$] stretching vibration for the uncomplex *p*-azo-carboxylate ligand (LHH') was observed at 1685 cm⁻¹. After complexation, this band appears to lower frequency at 1668 cm⁻¹ in Ph₃SnLH while in other complexes **1-6**, this frequency was found to be shifted further to 1625 cm⁻¹. The shift of band relative to its position for the ligands is owing to the carboxylate coordination to the

Scheme 1. Reaction scheme for the synthesis of tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes, **1-6**.

metal atom^{15,16}. Other absorption bands observed at 1590–1597 and 3442–3477 cm⁻¹ are due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{OH})$ stretching frequencies. After coordination, these two bands remain in the same position indicating -OH of the aromatic ring and the azo-methine nitrogen atom does not take part in the coordination to the tin-atom. The IR spectra of all the complexes indicated the coordination of ligand to tin atom via carboxylate oxygen atom. The infrared spectra carried out on the solid samples show all the expected bands for the ligands and the compounds. Absorption bands in the region 656–686 and 558–584 cm⁻¹ are assigned to $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$ and $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{O})$ respectively²².

¹H, ¹³C and ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra :

¹H, ¹³C and ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra of the synthesized complexes were recorded in CDCl₃ to determine the structural features of the complexes in the solution state. The spectral data of the complexes are given in the Experimental section. ¹H NMR spectra of the complexes show a singlet peak at around 8.7–8.9 ppm which may be assigned to C(H)=N proton, while the broad peaks at around 11.3–14.2 ppm are due to -OH protons. A singlet peak observed at 6.7 ppm in compound **4** may be assigned to -SO₂NH₂ protons. The ¹H NMR spectra of the complexes **5** and **6** show a singlet peak at 2.4 ppm which may be assigned to -CH₃ protons. The multiplets observed at around 6.7–8.3 are due to the protons of the aromatic ring while the multiplets appear at around 7.5 ppm and 7.8 ppm may be assigned to the Sn-Ph protons of the tri-

Fig. 2. Comparison of *in vitro* antifungal activity of the tri-phenyltin(IV) compounds.

Fig. 3. Comparison of *in vitro* antibacterial activity of the tri-phenyltin(IV) compounds.

phenyltin moiety respectively. In the ¹³C NMR spectra of all the complexes, the chemical shift values at 173, 165 and 161 ppm may be assigned to -CO₂, -C-OH and -C(H)=N respectively, while in the complexes **5** and **6**, the chemical shift observed at around 19 ppm is due to -CH₃ carbon. ¹¹⁹Sn NMR chemical shifts of the triphenyltin complexes, **1-6** were recorded in CDCl₃ using Me₄Sn as standard reference compound set at 0.0 ppm. ¹¹⁹Sn

NMR spectroscopy gives useful information to determine the coordination number around tin atom in the complexes in solution. The ^{119}Sn NMR spectra of the complexes, **1-6** show only one sharp resonance peak in the range -107.3 to -108.1 ppm which are well within the specified range for four-coordinate geometry (-40 to -120 ppm) and therefore, suggested to have four-coordinate tetrahedral structure for all the tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes in solution state^{23,24}.

Antimicrobial activities :

The *in vitro* antimicrobial activities of precursor Ph_3SnLH and the synthesised tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes **2-4** and **6** have been studied at different concentrations (5.0 mg mL^{-1} and 2.5 mg mL^{-1}) for zone of the inhibition of the compounds and compared with the standard drugs, Amphotericin-B for antifungal and Ciprofloxacin for antibacterial studies whereas serial dilution from the stock solution concentrations (5 mg mL^{-1}) for the MICs of the compounds. The zone of inhibition of these compounds against various fungi and bacteria strains is given in Table 1 while their MICs are presented in Table 2 along with the standard drugs. The MICs histogram chart for all the complexes along with the standard drugs have

also been presented in Figs. 2 and 3. It was observed that the ligand, LHH' is ineffective against all the fungus and the bacteria while the precursor tri-phenyltin(IV) compound, Ph_3SnLH and compounds **2** and **4** were found to be more effective antifungal agents against all the screened fungal strains. It was also found that the compounds **2** and **4** are more effective antifungal agents against *A. niger* but activity is less against *C. albicans*. In case of antibacterial activities, except **3** and **6**, all the other compounds were found to be effective against all the bacteria strain. The precursor compound, Ph_3SnLH and compounds **2** and **4** are more effective against *P. aeruginosa* whereas compounds **3** and **6** are inactive against *S. paratyphi*. From the above observation, it has been found that a particular tri-phenyltin(IV) compound exhibits different antifungal and antibacterial activity against different microbes. It was also found that compounds **2** and **4** are more effective antifungal and antibacterial agents as compared to the other tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes of this series. All the screened tri-phenyltin(IV) compounds exhibit better antifungal activities against *A. fumigatus* and *A. niger* as compared to other bacteria strains. Moreover, the compounds were found to be more effective

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity of tri-phenyltin(IV) compounds (zone of inhibition in mm)

Compds.	Zone of inhibitions of tested fungi (mm) at different concentrations									
	<i>A. flavus</i>		<i>A. fumigatus</i>		<i>A. niger</i>		<i>C. albicans</i>		<i>C. krusei</i>	
	5	2.5	5	2.5	5	2.5	5	2.5	5	2.5
LHH'	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ph_3SnLH	26	24	28	24	28	26	18	14	20	16
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnL}^2\text{H}$ (2)	24	20	26	22	30	28	20	16	22	20
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnL}^3\text{H}$ (3)	22	18	22	18	24	20	16	12	18	14
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnL}^4\text{H}$ (4)	28	24	28	26	30	28	20	16	22	20
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnL}^6\text{H}$ (6)	12	10	26	24	28	24	16	14	18	16
Amp-B (16 $\mu\text{g/mL}$)	32		34		38		38		40	
Compds.	Zone of inhibitions of tested bacteria (mm) at different concentrations									
	<i>P. mirabilis</i>		<i>K. pneumoniae</i>		<i>E. coli</i>		<i>S. paratyphi</i>		<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	
	5	2.5	5	2.5	5	2.5	5	2.5	5	2.5
LHH'	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ph_3SnLH	14	12	14	12	14	10	8	-	16	14
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnL}^2\text{H}$ (2)	14	12	14	12	14	10	10	8	16	14
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnL}^3\text{H}$ (3)	14	12	12	10	10	-	-	-	14	10
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnL}^4\text{H}$ (4)	16	14	16	12	14	12	12	8	16	14
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnL}^6\text{H}$ (6)	14	10	12	10	10	8	-	-	14	12
Cip (16 $\mu\text{g/mL}$)	32		34		36		36		34	

In vitro agar well-diffusion method, concentrations : 5 mg mL^{-1} and 2.5 mg mL^{-1} in DMSO, reference drugs, Amphotericin-B for antifungal test and Ciprofloxacin for antibacterial test : $16 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in DMSO dash (-) indicated inactivity.

Table 2. Minimum inhibition concentration (MIC) for antimicrobial activities of tri-phenyltin(IV) compounds

Compsds.	MIC for tested fungi (Concentration in $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)				
	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. fumigatus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>C. krusei</i>
Ph ₃ SnLH	>4.8	4.8	<4.8	>19.5	<19.5
Ph ₃ SnL ² H (2)	4.8	2.4	0.6	<19.5	4.8
Ph ₃ SnL ³ H (3)	9.7	9.7	4.8	78.1	>19.5
Ph ₃ SnL ⁴ H (4)	1.2	<1.2	0.6	>19.5	4.8
Ph ₃ SnL ⁶ H (6)	156.2	>4.8	>4.8	>19.5	19.5
Amphotericin-B	0.5	1.0	0.5	<0.5	>0.5
Compsds.	MIC for tested bacteria (Concentration in $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)				
	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. paratyphi</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
Ph ₃ SnLH	78.1	78.1	78.1	1250	>19.5
Ph ₃ SnL ² H (2)	78.1	78.1	>78.1	312.5	39.1
Ph ₃ SnL ³ H (3)	78.1	156.2	312.5	5000	78.1
Ph ₃ SnL ⁴ H (4)	19.5	78.1	78.1	312.5	19.5
Ph ₃ SnL ⁶ H (6)	156.2	156.2	312.5	5000	19.5
Ciprofloxacin	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5

against the fungi than the bacteria. The antimicrobial activity of the present tri-phenyltin(IV) compounds reported here are better than the tri-butyltin(IV) *para*-azo-carboxylates reported earlier¹⁹, however, the activities are lower than the standard drugs.

Proposed structure of the complexes :

Efforts for getting single crystals suitable for X-crystal structure analysis could not be achieved however, from the X-ray crystal structure analysis of tri-organotin(IV) complexes of the similar ligand systems reported earlier¹⁸; the complexes are proposed to adopt tetrahedral geometry in solid state (Scheme 1). It was also reported that only one oxygen atom of carboxylate ligand coordinate to tin atom in tri-organotin *para*-azo-carboxylates, the coordination from another chelating oxygen atom of carboxylate group is not considered because the interaction is very weak and the bond is too long to consider for five-coordinate geometry around tin atom. In addition to this, the bond angles are in consistent with four-coordinate tetrahedral environments than five-coordinate trigonal bi-pyramidal environment and therefore, it is suggested that the present tri-phenyltin(IV) compounds have monomeric tetrahedral structures both in solution and solid states¹⁸. Tri-organotin(IV) carboxylates often adopt oligomeric and trigonal bipyramidal geometry^{15,16}. The same was found true in case of organotin(IV) *ortho*-azo-carboxylate ligand systems in which tri-organotin(IV) car-

boxylates adopt polymeric and trigonal bipyramidal geometry. The difference in the structural motifs of tri-organotin(IV) complexes of *ortho*- and *para*-azo-carboxylates may be due to the different synthetic routes adopted. In case of *ortho*-azo-carboxylates, complete condensed azo-imino-carboxylates were first prepared and reacted with appropriate tri-organotin(IV) precursors whereas in case of *para* analogues, owing to the insolubility nature of the pre ligand in common organic solvents, tri-alkyltin(IV) complex of *para*-azo-ligand was first prepared and then condensed with appropriate aniline derivatives to give the desired extended azo-imino ligands with monomeric tetrahedral structures.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Ph₃SnOH was prepared from Ph₃SnCl (Merck) following the literature method²⁵. Salicylaldehyde and substituted anilines (reagent grade) were used without further purification. AR grade solvents were used in all the reactions and dried using standard procedures. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analysis were performed with a Perkin-Elmer 2400 series II instrument. Electronic spectra of the compounds were recorded on UV-1800 Shimadzu spectrophotometer in DMF in the range of 200–800 nm. IR spectra in the range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹ were obtained on Shimadzu FT-IR-8400S spectrophotometer using KBr discs. The ¹H, ¹³C and ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra were recorded

on a Bruker AMX 400 spectrophotometer and measured at 400.13, 100.62 and 149.18 MHz respectively. ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{119}Sn NMR chemical shifts were referred to Me_4Si set at 0.00 ppm, CDCl_3 at 77.00 ppm and Me_4Sn at 0.00 ppm respectively.

Synthesis of 4-(3-formyl-4-hydroxy-phenylazo)-benzoic acid (LHH') :

The ligand LHH' [Fig. 1(a)] was prepared by following the reported procedure¹⁸. Yield : 65%; m.p. 276–278 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$: C, 62.22; H, 3.70; N, 10.37%. Found : C, 61.75; H, 3.58; N, 10.15%; UV-Vis (DMF) λ_{max} (nm) : 247, 322; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1680 $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$; ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$, ppm) : 7.25 [1H, d, (A) H5], 7.96 [2H, m, (B) H2 and H6], 8.14 [1H, dd, (A) H6], 8.17 [2H, m, (B) H3 and H5], 8.27 [1H, d, (A) H2], 10.35 [1H, s, C(H)=O].

Synthesis of 4-(4-hydroxy-3-phenyliminomethyl-phenylazo)-benzoic acids ($\text{L}^{1-6}\text{HH}'$) :

The condensed azo-imino ligands ($\text{L}^{1-6}\text{HH}'$) [Fig. 1(b)] could not be prepared owing to the insolubility nature of the precursor *p*-azo-benzoic acid ligand (LHH') in common organic solvents. If *p*-azo-benzoic acid ligand were soluble in common organic solvents, direct condensation of the azo-carboxylate ligand and aniline derivatives would have been possible. However, the ligand frameworks of the condensed ligands ($\text{L}^{1-6}\text{HH}'$) were generated *in situ* during the reaction of Ph_3SnLH with the appropriate substituted anilines.

Synthesis of Ph_3SnLH :

The compound was synthesized by following the earlier report¹⁸. Yield : 34%; m.p. 180–182 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Sn}$: C, 62.41; H, 3.90; N, 4.52%. Found : C, 62.57; H, 4.14; N, 4.70%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1660 $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 7.14 [1H, d, (B) H5], 7.49 [9H, m, Sn-Ph (H3* and H4*)], 7.83 [6H, m, Sn-Ph (H2*)], 7.93 [2H, d, (B) H2 and H6], 8.21 [1H, d, (A) H6], 8.24 [1H, d, (A) H2], 8.30 [2H, d, (B) H3 and H6], 10.08 [1H, s, C(H)=O], 11.40 [1H, br, OH].

Synthesis of $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnL}^1\text{H}$ (1) :

The compound $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnL}^1\text{H}$ (1) was prepared by adding dropwise hot ethanol solution of 4-nitro aniline (0.64 mmol in 15 mL ethanol) to Ph_3SnLH (0.64 mmol in 30 mL ethanol) while stirring and followed by refluxing the reaction mixture for 3 h and then filtered while hot. The

residue was dried in vacuum, washed with hexane and then extracted from chloroform. The crude product obtained after evaporation was recrystallized from chloroform-hexane mixture to yield orange crystalline product. Yield : 45%; m.p. 122–124 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{Sn}$: C, 61.70; H, 3.78; N, 7.57%. Found : C, 61.58; H, 3.61; N, 7.39%; UV-Vis (DMF) λ_{max} (nm) : 252, 376, 474; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3442 $\nu(\text{OH})$, 1618 $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$, 667 $\nu(\text{Sn-C})$, 536 $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 6.63–8.25 [11H, m, Ar-H], 7.51 [9H, m, Sn-Ph (H3* and H4*)], 7.85 [6H, m, Sn-Ph (H2*)], 8.77 [1H, s, C(H)=N], 13.2 [1H, br, OH]; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 163.39 [C(H)=N], 163.52 [C-OH], 170.9 [CO₂]; other carbons : 112.53, 118.25, 119.35, 121.16, 121.61, 124.50, 125.52, 128.20, 129.48, 130.88, 136.13, 137.34, 139.95, 141.16, 151.15, 154.26; ^{119}Sn NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : -107.56. The other tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes were synthesized following the analogous procedure by the condensation reaction of precursor tri-phenyltin(IV) complex [Ph_3SnLH] with appropriate aniline derivatives. The characterization and spectroscopic data of the tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes 2-6 are given below.

Synthesis of $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnL}^2\text{H}$ (2) :

Yield : 50%; m.p. 122–124 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{ClSn}$: C, 62.59; H, 3.84; N, 5.76%. Found : C, 62.47; H, 3.65; N, 5.62%; UV-Vis (DMF) λ_{max} (nm) : 252, 372, 472; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3434 $\nu(\text{OH})$, 1618 $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$, 697 $\nu(\text{Sn-C})$, 504 $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 7.7–8.3 [11H, m, Ar-H], 8.74 [1H, s, C(H)=N], 10.04 [1H, br, OH], 7.41 [9H, m, Sn-Ph (H3* and H4*)], 7.88 [6H, m, Sn-Ph (H2*)]; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 161.62 [C(H)=N], 164.9 [C-OH], 173.8 [CO₂]; other carbons : 115.63, 117.25, 119.75, 121.9, 122.79, 125.83, 126.32, 128.19, 129.60, 131.71, 132.79, 137.21, 145.18, 146.31, 152.74, 154.46; ^{119}Sn NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : -108.

Synthesis of $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnL}^3\text{H}$ (3) :

Yield : 60%; m.p. 118–120 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Sn}$: C, 64.22; H, 4.08; N, 5.91%. Found : C, 64.11; H, 3.97; N, 5.77%; UV-Vis (DMF) λ_{max} (nm) : 258, 376, 455; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3452 $\nu(\text{OH})$, 1631 $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$, 673 $\nu(\text{Sn-C})$, 517 $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 7.82–8.31 [11H, m, Ar-H], 8.98 [1H, s, C(H)=N], 12.99 [1H, br, (A) OH], 13.03 [1H, br, (B) OH], 7.48 [9H, m, Sn-Ph (H3* and H4*)], 7.82 [6H, m, Sn-Ph

(H2*); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 161.17 [C(H)=N], 163.26 [C-OH], 171.19 [CO_2]; other carbons : 118.75, 122.40, 124.57, 125.15, 128.65, 129.21, 129.38, 130.48, 131.91, 135.21, 136.74, 138.28, 139.06, 141.57, 145.78, 151.35, 155.16, 159.13; ^{119}Sn NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : -107.9.

Synthesis of $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnL}^4\text{H}$ (4) :

Yield : 36%; m.p. 74–76 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{SSn}$: C, 58.99; H, 3.88; N, 7.24%. Found : C, 58.76; H, 3.70; N, 7.13%; UV-Vis (DMF) λ_{max} (nm) : 252, 378, 477; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3436 $\nu(\text{OH})$, 1622 $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$, 1067 $\nu(\text{N-H})$, 692 $\nu(\text{Sn-C})$, 558 $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 6.7 [2H, s, NH_2], 7.89–8.31 [11H, m, Ar-H], 8.75 [1H, s, C(H)=N], 11.39 [1H, br, OH], 7.49 [9H, m, Sn-Ph (H3* and H4*)], 7.71 [6H, m, Sn-Ph (H2*)]; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 162.29 [C(H)=N], 163.93 [C-OH], 172.31 [CO_2]; other carbons : 116.61, 118.39, 121.35, 123.15, 128.21, 128.59, 130.48, 132.17, 133.79, 136.25, 139.18, 144.88, 146.69, 151.25, 154.89, 159.15; ^{119}Sn NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : -108.10.

Synthesis of $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnL}^5\text{H}$ (5) :

Yield : 58%; m.p. 155–158 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{39}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{Sn}$: C, 66.10; H, 4.37; N, 5.93%. Found : C, 65.96; H, 4.29; N, 5.79%; UV-Vis (DMF) λ_{max} (nm) : 256, 359, 476; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3445 $\nu(\text{OH})$, 1622 $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$, 665 $\nu(\text{Sn-C})$, 584 $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 2.43 [3H, s, CH_3], 7.83–8.31 [11H, m, Ar-H], 8.75 [1H, s, C(H)=N], 14.07 [1H, br, OH], 7.48 [9H, m, Sn-Ph (H3* and H4*)], 7.84 [6H, m, Sn-Ph (H2*)]; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 21.30 [CH_3], 161.61 [C(H)=N], 164.75 [C-OH], 172.8 [CO_2]; other carbons : 118.05, 118.29, 118.85, 121.86, 122.17, 127.53, 128.13, 128.36, 129.27, 130.15, 131.59, 136.37, 138.14, 139.43, 145.81, 147.47, 151.27, 154.25; ^{119}Sn NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : -107.35.

Synthesis of $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnL}^6\text{H}$ (6) :

Yield : 58%; m.p. 130–132 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{39}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{Sn}$: C, 66.10; H, 4.37; N, 5.93%. Found : C, 65.99; H, 4.24; N, 5.74%; UV-Vis (DMF) λ_{max} (nm) : 253, 356, 459; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3445 $\nu(\text{OH})$, 1631 $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$, 656 $\nu(\text{Sn-C})$, 584 $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 2.45 [3H, s, CH_3], 7.83–8.32 [11H, m, Ar-H], 8.71 [1H, s, C(H)=N], 14.24 [1H, br, OH], 7.51 [9H, m, Sn-Ph (H3* and H4*)], 7.84 [6H, m, Sn-Ph (H2*)]; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 18.17 [CH_3], 161.45

[C(H)=N], 164.83 [C-OH], 173.0 [CO_2]; other carbons : 117.63, 118.28, 118.96, 121.38, 122.19, 127.32, 128.91, 130.18, 130.82, 131.61, 132.37, 132.56, 136.88, 138.13, 139.75, 146.8, 151.81, 154.15; ^{119}Sn NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : -107.75.

The numbering scheme of Sn-phenyl skeleton is given below :

Antifungal and antibacterial test :

The antimicrobial activity was assessed by agar well diffusion method using 20 mL of sterile nutrient agar (Hi-Media) and potato-dextrose agar (Hi-Media) and sabouraud dextrose agar (Hi-Media) for testing the bacterial and fungal activity²⁶. The test cultures were swabbed on the top of the solidified media and allowed to dry for 10 min. Sterile 6 mm diameter cork borer were pierced in the agar. Each compound was diluted in 5 mg/mL in DMSO and diluted again. The dilution of the compounds concentration were deposited 20 μL on the inoculated well and left for 10 min at room temperature for the compound diffusion. Negative control was prepared using DMSO while Amphotericin-B (Hi-Media) for fungi and Ciprofloxacin (Hi-Media) for bacteria were served as positive control. The plates were inoculated with bacteria and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. For fungal the plates were inoculated at 30 °C for 24–48 h. The experiment was repeated thrice and the average results were recorded. The antimicrobial activity was determined by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone (mm) around the well. The susceptibility of microbial was determined by minimum inhibitory concentration determination method²⁷. The MIC was evaluated on plant extracts that showed antibacterial activity in the agar well diffusion assay on any organism. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) of the compounds were determined by serial dilution against the micro-organisms. The minimum concentrations at which no visible growth were observed is defined as the MICs, which were expressed in $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The fungi, and bacteria employed in the test are *A. flavus*, *A. fumigates*, *A. niger*, *C. albicans*, *C. krusei* and *P. mirabilis*,

K. pneumonia, *E. coli*, *S. paratyphi*, *P. aeruginosa* respectively.

Conclusion

Tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes of *para*-azo-carboxylate have been synthesized, characterized and studied for their *in vitro* antimicrobial activities against various fungal and bacterial species. The UV and IR spectral study of the complexes indicated the coordination of the carboxylate ligand to tin atom. ¹¹⁹Sn NMR study of the complexes suggested four-coordinate geometry around tin atom and therefore, proposed to have tetrahedral structure of the complexes in solution state. From the X-ray structure analysis of the similar ligand systems reported earlier¹⁸, the structure of the complexes is proposed to have monomeric tetrahedral geometry. The antifungal and antibacterial activity of tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes were investigated against different microbes and their minimum inhibitory concentrations were also determined against the tested microbes and finally compared with standard drugs. Among the tested compounds, the precursor tri-phenyltin(IV) complex, Ph₃SnLH and the tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes, **2** and **4** were found to be more effective antimicrobial agents against the tested microbes as compared to the other tri-phenyltin(IV) complexes of this series.

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